

Optimal investments into rooftop solar and batteries for a distribution grid company and prosumers: A case study in India

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Abstract— Rooftop solar power plants, hereafter rooftop solar, have good potential to decarbonize local energy systems in countries like India. This paper investigates optimal sizing of rooftop solar together with lithium-ion batteries from the perspectives of distribution grid companies and prosumers. For this, a techno-economic analysis is performed on a case study in Delhi using an optimization tool, the Multi-Vector Simulator. Results indicate that with current incentives it is an economically attractive option for domestic consumers to invest in rooftop solar to become prosumers, while investments in battery storage do not lead to economic benefits. However, the availability of upfront investments and roof areas could limit the growth of prosumers. For distribution grid companies growing prosumers means a reduction in revenues. By investing in rooftop solar, distribution grid companies can improve their profitability and self-meet their obligation to purchase renewable energy. For policymakers, it is important to design policy instruments that support both the prosumers as well as the grid operators.

Keywords—Rooftop solar, battery storage, distribution grid companies, prosumerism

I. INTRODUCTION

Prosumerism refers to the phenomenon where traditional energy consumers are transforming into actors who are both producing as well as consuming renewable energy, i.e., prosumers [1]. In India, prosumerism through rooftop solar is seen as an attractive option. The abundance of sun, falling PV panel costs, relative ease of installation and supportive government policies are key contributors to the rise of rooftop solar based prosumers [2]. Electricity distribution companies have to react appropriately to these changes to make use of the potentials and meet the impacts of this trend.

In short term, the government of India has set a target of 100 GW grid-connected solar power generation by 2022, of which 40 GW are expected to come from rooftop solar [3]. It is expected that more than half of the rooftop potential is in the residential/domestic sector [4]. Delhi had a peak power demand of about 6 GW in 2014. To meet the national renewable generation target and to lead India's rooftop revolution, Delhi has set an aggressive target to generate 2 GW (about 6.6% of yearly demand) from rooftop solar by 2025 [5].

Rooftop solar have both positive and negative impacts on distribution grids. On the positive side, rooftop solar are expected to shave peak demand, reduce distribution power losses, increase the security of supply and improve voltage

profile [6], [7]. However, at the same time, unmanaged high rooftop solar penetration can lead to several operational challenges for grid operators. Some of the challenges are reverse power flows, overvoltage, inadequate power factor and unwanted harmonics [8].

Grid-connected energy storage technologies present opportunities to overcome the negative impacts of rooftop solar, improve the reliability of the distribution grid and integrate a higher share of renewables [9]. Lithium-ion batteries are one of the mature technologies available in the market and have the required characteristics to be an attractive investment option for both the distribution grids and for prosumers [10]. Although the cost of lithium-ion batteries is decreasing, it still entails significant investment costs. Thus, it is crucial that such batteries are cost-optimally sized for their application.

The goal of this paper is to investigate optimal investment into rooftop solar and battery for both, the prosumers (which are currently consumers) and the electricity distribution companies (DISCOMs). A sub-goal of the paper is to assess the effect of growing prosumerism on the business of DISCOMs in India. For this, a techno-economic assessment of rooftop solar and battery technologies is performed using the Multi-Vector Simulator (MVS) [10], an investment and energy system optimization tool. A residential neighbourhood in Delhi is used as a case study.

II. CASE STUDY

BSES Yamuna Power Ltd. (BYPL) is a DISCOM operating in central and east Delhi. It has 1.73 million consumers, a peak load of 1.7 GW and an annual electricity requirement of 7,183 GWh [11]. The case study considered in the paper is a section of the BYPL operation area called Saini enclave. It receives electricity from the 33kV national grid through a 20 MVA regional transformer. The load at Saini Enclave is met by 5 transformers of 990 kVA and 5 transformers of 630 kVA ratings. The peak annual demand of Saini enclave is 3.5 MW with electricity requirements of 11.9 GWh/year. Saini enclave predominantly comprises domestic customers (about 82%). The remaining customers are commercial buildings. Currently no domestic rooftop solar is installed in Saini enclave. There is however a 7 kW rooftop solar plant and 10 kWh battery installed at BYPL office in the same area.

Currently, domestic consumers can avail two incentives for grid-connected rooftop solar. First is the subsidy provided

by the Indian government which covers 40% of investment cost up to 3 kW system size and 20% thereafter until 10 kW [12]. Second, there is a feed-in tariff that the DISCOM is obligated to provide, and this is the same as the average purchase cost of electricity for DISCOM. In addition to the incentives received by domestic customers, DISCOMs can benefit from selling renewable energy certificates (RECs). For each kWh of renewable energy generated in the operation area of a DISCOM, it can avail a REC which can be sold in the open market [13].

To achieve the targets set by the Delhi government, the renewable purchase obligation (RPO) obliges DISCOMs in Delhi to purchase a defined percentage of their demand from renewable sources [13]. The DISCOM has to pay a penalty fee for every unit of electricity that is not met under the obligation. Fig. 1 shows the solar RPO target set by the Delhi government from the financial year 2017 till 2022. The figure also shows that BYPL did not meet the RPO targets until FY 19-20. In the figure future failure to meet the RPO targets are estimated based upon the linear project of the historic trend.

Fig. 1. Solar RPO set by Delhi government compared to actual RPO met by DISCOM. FY = financial year. (*) = estimated value based upon linear historic projection. Source: own depiction based upon [13].

Considering incentives and penalties, both prosumers and DISCOMs can benefit from investing in rooftop solar and batteries (lithium-ion). This study investigates optimal investment strategies in rooftop solar and battery for both the above-mentioned actors using Saini enclave as the case study. In India, DISCOMs play the dual role of being a grid operator and a retailer. Therefore, it is of particular interest to BYPL (the DISCOM) to investigate if they can avail benefits by investing in rooftop solar themselves. Since Saini enclave is a densely populated area majorly of domestic customers only rooftop solar is deemed feasible.

III. METHOD

A. Scenarios

For the assessment, seven scenarios are created in each of which rooftop solar and battery capacities are optimized using the optimization tool MVS. Furthermore, the impact of investments on the business of the DISCOM is also evaluated in each of the scenarios. Scenario 1 is used as a benchmark for rest of the scenarios.

1) *Scenario 1, Business-as-usual (BAU)*, based on current grid capacity and already installed rooftop solar and battery which is owned by the DISCOM (BYPL). In this scenario, there are only consumers and no prosumers with rooftop solar. 100% of the consumer demand are supplied by the grid. Currently, the DISCOM purchases the bulk of its power

through long term purchase agreements and thus a fixed average electricity purchase cost is considered. The electricity purchased is sold to the end consumer at a different selling price determined by the regulator. Differences in purchase and selling prices result in revenue for the DISCOM.

2) *Scenario 2, Grid optimal scenario*, in which optimal investments into grid-scale batteries and PV capacity by the DISCOM are assessed to minimize their energy supply costs. This can be achieved by generating cheap solar electricity, taking advantage of RECs.

3) *Scenario 3, Power market scenario*, same as previous but instead of the fixed electricity purchase price, hourly prices based on the power exchange prices are considered. The goal is to investigate if BYPL can improve its profitability by buying electricity directly from the power exchange market and if storage can reduce expenditures by shifting imports away from times with high electricity prices.

4) *Scenario 4, Short-term optimal scenario*, similar to scenario 2 but maximum PV installation capacity is capped to 500 kW. The DISCOM owns a few buildings which can provide enough roof area for a maximum of 500 kW of PV plants. It is assumed that only these buildings are available for installing rooftop solar in the short term.

5) *Scenario 5, Prosumer optimal scenario*, in which the cost-optimal investment is investigated from the perspective of domestic prosumers. This includes investments into rooftop solar and residential batteries considering guaranteed feed-in tariffs that prosumers have. The prosumers can install as much PV as is optimal for reaching minimum net present costs subject to that the feed-in do not exceed 80% of the transformer station rating. No space constraints are considered in the study.

6) *Scenario 6, Limited prosumerism*, in which the aggregated PV capacity which can be installed by prosumers in Saini enclave is limited to the capacity targeted by the Delhi government (33% of the local demand, i.e., 1.2 MW).

7) *Scenario 7, Adaption to limited prosumerism scenario*, in which the DISCOM invests into optimal energy asset capacities (PV & batteries) in response to limited prosumerism (scenario 6).

Scenarios 2 to 4 are designed to understand how the DISCOM should plan its investments to minimize expenditures and thus maximize profits. These scenarios assume the REC can be sold by DISCOM throughout the project period without any limitations. Scenarios 5 and 6 are designed to understand prosumers point of view and how they should be planning their investments to reduce their electricity costs.

B. Simulation model

The case study scenarios are analysed using the open-source investment planning tool Multi-Vector Simulator (MVS) [10]. At its core, it utilizes the Open Energy Modelling Framework (oemof) [14], specifically oemof-solph [15], to generate energy system models adapted to the user inputs. The user can choose between multiple energy vectors as well as production, consumption, conversion and storage assets. The MVS then determines the optimal asset capacities and their dispatch, to minimize annual energy supply costs. The post-

processing evaluates the performance of the energy system by calculating a few pre-defined key performance indicators.

For the current study, the demand by Saini enclave is supplied from the following sources: grid imports into the DISCOM area, local renewable generation or battery dispatch on the DISCOM feeders or, dependent on the scenario, local domestic renewable generation or domestic battery dispatch. Real-life constraints of the grid in form of transformer stations are introduced. For future investments, rooftop solar is modelled as a non-dispatchable energy production asset that is defined through a time series of the specific PV generation profile over the simulation period of one year in hourly values. A detailed description of the energy system modelling with the MVS is beyond the scope of this work and readers are referred to the MVS documentation [10].

C. Assessment indicators

In this study the key set of economic and technical indicators used for assessment are:

- Net present value (NPV): Total net present value in Euro of supplying Saini enclave with electricity over the project lifetime of 35 years, including investment and replacement costs as well as operating expenditures of energy assets (rooftop solar and battery) and revenues for supplying the residential consumers. This indicator is applicable only to the DISCOM.
- Net present cost (NPC): Total net present cost of energy assets (rooftop solar and battery) and cost of buying electricity from the grid for project lifetime of 35 years. This includes installation, maintenance and replacement costs of energy assets. This indicator is only applicable to prosumers.
- Upfront investment costs (IC): Total costs in year zero in Euro to procure the optimized energy system assets.
- Annuity of investments (A): Annuity of the investment, replacement and running costs of optimized PV and battery assets in Euro per year,
- Renewable energy share (RES): Share of the demand that is covered by the local renewable generation from an aggregated perspective, i.e. not in-time supply.

These key indicators are supplemented with additional indicators to assess scenarios in more detail. These indicators are yearly expenditures through electricity purchase, yearly revenues through electricity sales and incentives, rooftop solar feed-in, annual rooftop solar generation and rooftop area needed for installation.

D. Modelling input data

Measurements by BYPL (DISCOM) is provided of the yearly demand profile in 15 minutes resolution from the year 2018. Pre-processing removed the outliers and filled data gaps to generate an hourly time series. The PV generation profile is obtained from the open-source database Renewables.ninja [16]. The project lifetime is considered to be 35 years based upon the current maximum lifetime of PV panels. In this study, no degradation of PV panel and battery over their lifetime is considered. BYPL has a stepped tariff system of electricity prices based upon yearly consumption range and peak connection capacity. Most of the domestic customers consume electricity in the range of 801 to 1,200

kWh/year and have connections less than 5 kW. This study assumed that all customers fall in this category and pay the same electricity price. Fixed prices based upon peak connection is not considered as demand profile is not available on individual customer level but only on the aggregated level of the distribution transformer.

Table I provides further techno-economic parameters assumed in the simulations, while Table II provide the electricity tariffs for import and export. REC selling prices vary in the market, however, a fixed cost based upon consultation with DISCOM is assumed.

TABLE I. ASSUMPTIONS USED FOR MODELLING ENERGY SYSTEM.

Parameter	Value	Unit
<i>Battery storage</i>		
Battery storage, 11 kV (quotation received by BYPL)		
-Investment cost (incl. installation)	403.59	Euro/kWh
-O&M cost (@10% of investment cost)	40.36	Euro/kWh/year
Battery storage, 415 V and domestic level (quotation received by BYPL)		
-Investment cost (includes installation costs)	691.87	Euro/kWh
-O&M cost, 415 V (@5% of investment cost)	34.59	Euro/kWh/year
-O&M cost, residential	0	Euro/kWh/year
Battery lifetime	10	Years
C rate for battery storage	1	NA
Throughput efficiency	95	Percent
<i>PV</i>		
Commercial PV plant, BYPL [17]		
-Panel investment cost (incl. installation costs)	410.17	Euro/kW
-Panel O&M costs (@1.5% of installation costs)	6.76	Euro/kW/year
-Inverter investment cost (@11% of PV investment cost) [18]	49.9	Euro/kW
Domestic PV plant [17]		
-Subsidy on investment costs	20	Percent
-Panel investment cost (incl. installation costs)	341.87	Euro/kW
-Panel O&M costs (@1.5% of installation costs)	5.20	Euro/kW/year
-Inverter investment cost (@11% of PV investment cost) [18]	61.55	Euro/kW
PV lifetime	35	years
Inverter lifetime	15	years
Rooftop area needed per kW [5]	12	Sq..m
<i>Other</i>		
Discount factor (Provided by BYPL)	12	Percent
Project lifetime	35	Years
Approx. Area of Saini enclave	1	M Sq.m

TABLE II. VARIOUS TARIFFS CONSIDERED IN THE STUDY.

Tariffs	Value	Unit
<i>DISCOM (BYPL)</i>		
Electricity purchase cost, average (Provided by BYPL)	0.0492	Euro/kWh

Electricity export tariff to the national grid	0	Euro/kWh
REC selling price for DISCOM	0.0115	Euro/kWh
<i>Domestic consumers/prosumers</i>		
Average sales price to consumers (revenue for BYPL)	0.0807	Euro/kWh
Feed-in tariff for consumers (expenditures for BYPL)	0.0492	Euro/kWh

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Due to the 20% state subsidy on PV assets including inverters, the levelized cost of rooftop solar for domestic prosumers is 0.035 Euro/kWh which is about half of the electricity purchase price from the DISCOM and lower than the feed-in tariff for prosumers. The DISCOM has a slightly higher levelized cost of rooftop solar of 0.0415 Euro/kWh without REC gains while with REC gains it is 0.030 Euro/kWh, in both of these cases it is lower than the average purchase price for the DISCOM. Favourable levelized costs indicate that there is a good potential to replace grid imports with local generation during the day if sufficient area is available.

A. DISCOM driven investments

Table III shows the results of the scenarios designed to investigate the DISCOM perspective. Currently, the DISCOM has a marginal renewable share. It can be observed that in the investment scenarios S2-S4 the optimal size of battery storage is zero. This suggests that investing in a battery solution is not cost-effective considering its benefits, i.e., the margin that can be saved by increased self-consumption from rooftop solar. Rooftop solar, therefore, is mainly used to cover daytime demand. It should be investigated further that at which price level the investment in battery becomes cost-effective. Batteries also provide additional values like improvement in voltage profile, power quality improvement and emergency backup which are not considered in this study. The cost-effectiveness of batteries by stacking multiple values from it should be analysed further.

The DISCOM could benefit from installing its own PV plants, as scenario 2 shows that profits can be increased if sufficient rooftop area is available. Scenario 3 results in the highest NPV, showing that the DISCOM can benefit from both installing rooftop PV and buying electricity through the power market. Still, benefits accrued from avoiding electricity purchase as well as arbitrage from power exchange are also not enough in making battery an attractive investment option.

In scenarios 2 and 3, the optimal PV size is more than 33% of peak demand and 7% yearly demand (exceeding the targets of the Delhi solar policy locally). This would require 4% of the Saini enclave area, exceeding the available rooftop area from the DISCOM owned buildings by multitudes. To access sufficient rooftop area, it might be interesting for BYPL to consider business models that could give them access to the rooftops of commercial, or even residential buildings.

The short-term investment scenario 4 shows marginal increases of the NPV. This results in 7% RES which

approximately fulfils the RPO targets for FY 2020-2021, and thus can save BYPL the penalty fees which they otherwise need to pay. It is interesting to note that the saved penalties of this one year are equivalent to half of the annuity of the investment into solar generation.

TABLE III. RESULTS FROM SCENARIOS SHOWCASING THE DISCOM PERSPECTIVE. S=SCENARIO.

Parameters	Scenarios - DISCOM perspective				
	<i>BAU (S1) - DISCOM perspective</i>	S2	S3	S4	S7
<i>Asset capacities</i>					
Optimal PV capacity (MW)	0	3.05	2.12	0.5	1.8 (+1.2 Prosumers)
Optimal battery capacity (MWh)	NA	0	0	0	0
<i>Indicators</i>					
NPV (MEuro)	2.98	3.5	4.28	3.1	2.76
RES	Negligible	32%	28%	7%	25%
IC (MEuros)	NA	1.31	0.91	0.22	0.79
Rooftop PV generation (GWh)	NA	4.83	3.36	0.8	0.8
Rooftop PV feed-in (GWh)	Negligible	0.58	0.14	0	0.6
DISCOM gains from selling RECs (kEuro/yr)	Negligible	43.9	38.7	9.2	33.7
A (kEuro/yr)	0	127	89	21	77
Area as % of Saini enclave	NA	4%	3%	1%	2%

B. Prosumer driven investments

Results from prosumer perspectives are summarized in Table IV. Prosumerism is financially attractive and in both scenarios 5 and 6 results in decreased electricity bills. In scenario 5, where the limit of prosumerism is defined by an export maximum of 80% of the transformer capacity rating, the optimal rooftop PV capacity amounts to about 13 MW. For these investments, the government would have to pay subsidies of 1.18 million Euro. This is a significant amount that can cause a burden on the government funds and is an important consideration for policymakers in future.

The optimized capacity is the aggregated capacity of all the decentralized prosumers at Saini enclave. Optimal rooftop PV capacity in scenario 5 is excessive, as rooftop solar is covering the peak demand and at the same time supplying the maximum power to the grid which prosumers are allowed to feed-in (about 8 MW), effectively translating into a profitable revenue stream for the prosumers. When demand is low but generation high, PV generation is partially curtailed due to the export limitation while still being profitable. The high exports could cause issues on the voltage and power quality side and induce expenses for the DISCOM. However, based upon BYPL an internal study 100% of transformer capacity can be utilized for feed-in from prosumers without any negative impact.

The implementation of scenario 5 would result in significant revenue losses for the DISCOM (see Fig. 2) and also result in high subsidies burden on the government, thus scenario 6 is introduced. The assumption is that subsidies are only available until Delhi rooftop solar targets are achieved,

i.e., 33% of the local demand peak which is about 1.2 MW. The DISCOM does not allow prosumerism after this point. Given the current benefits, i.e., the levelized cost of PV generation lower than the feed-in tariff, the prosumers should install exactly the allowed capacity of 1.2 MW. In both scenarios 5 and 6, no battery storage was observed. This is because batteries increase the per-unit costs of internal electricity supply and at the same time it is a more attractive option to sell excess generation due to the available feed-in tariff.

It is questionable whether these large rooftop solar capacities for prosumers would in reality be feasible. Specifically, three important bottlenecks that can inhibit prosumerism are discussed: The first bottleneck is the unavailability of finances to cover upfront investment costs which also has been a key roadblock for the growth of rooftop solar in India [19]. The second bottleneck is the availability of sufficient rooftop area. For scenario 5, 13 MW would require a rooftop area equal to 15% of the Saini enclave area. Considering the dense urban landscape of the case study, this area is high and might be unrealistic. With a required area for rooftop PV of 1% of Saini enclave, scenario 6 is much more likely to be feasible. As a next step, the available rooftop area of Saini enclave should be estimated, e.g. using geoinformation system (GIS) methods. Further rooftop areas might also already have defined uses and therefore may not be available for re-purposing. Thirdly, many of the domestic customers live in the multi-storey buildings sharing the common rooftop area. This limits how much rooftop solar each customer (or prosumer) can install and adds further complexity if joint ownership of the roof is considered.

TABLE IV. RESULTS OF SCENARIOS SHOWCASING PROSUMER PERSPECTIVE.

Parameters	Scenarios – Prosumerism		
	BAU - prosumer perspective	S5	S6
<i>Optimal capacities</i>			
Optimal PV capacity (MW)	0	12.9	1.2
Optimal battery capacity (MWh)	0	0	0
<i>Performance indicators</i>			
Collective NPC for all prosumers (MEuro)	7.87	4.6	7.23
RES	0%	172%	16%
IC (MEuros)	0	4.72	0.43
Rooftop PV feed-in (GWh)	0	12.97	0.01
Yearly savings (reduction in bill + feed-in tariff, kEur/yr)	0	444	140
A (kEur/yr)	0	678	62
Govt. subsidy used for residential rooftop PV investments (MEuros)	0	1.18	0.11
Rooftop area as % of Saini enclave	0%	15%	1%

C. DISCOM reaction to limited prosumerism

Prosumerism can reduce the annual revenues of the DISCOM, upto 45% as compared to BAU in scenario 6. However, such an extensive growth of prosumerism is unlikely while limited prosumerism is likely to happen where revenues are reduced by 16% (scenario 5). To assess whether

these losses could be mitigated scenario 7 is assessed. It turns out that the best response to 1.2 MW of prosumer solar rooftop installation would be to also install into a PV capacity of 1.8 MW on the DISCOM side as well. Such a decision would result in reduced losses of 27.000 Euro per year, and therefore the best NPV considering the situation.

D. Contextualization of DISCOM perspective

Fig. 2 shows the impact of different scenarios on the DISCOM business by considering two indicators, yearly profits and yearly revenue. If the DISCOM is investing in rooftop solar it can improve its profitability (Scenario 2 and 3). Even in scenario 3 where the DISCOM only installs rooftop solar on top of their own buildings, the effect is positive. However, in this case, the DISCOM would fall short by more than half the needed capacity in supporting Delhi's rooftop solar target.

Fig. 2. DISCOM profit and yearly revenue in all investigated scenarios.

In scenarios 2, 3 and 7 the DISCOM is able to meet the RPO targets as mandated by the regulator, whereas the short-term scenario 4 almost meets this target for 2020-21. At the same time, it is not evident whether the DISCOM is able to have access to sufficient rooftop area to implement larger PV capacities. Private as well as commercial rooftop owners may need incentives to allow the DISCOM to use their roofs for solar applications, which will reduce the benefits of the DISCOM.

Some of the input parameters to the model like electricity prices, REC price, feed-in tariff and investment costs, are considered constant over the project lifetime but in reality are likely to change over time. Therefore, a sensitivity analysis needs to be performed on key inputs. This shall help the DISCOM to make more informed decisions in long term. As the DISCOMs in India have a dual role of grid operator and retailer, the growth of prosumerism shall have a negative impact on its business. At the same time, consumers have a challenge with having upfront investment costs for becoming prosumers. This opens opportunities to explore new business models which could support prosumerism and avoid its negative impact on the DISCOM business. New business models could also reduce the need for government funds for various incentives. The design of new business models need to be investigated further.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper investigates the economic effect of installing rooftop solar and batteries on the DISCOMs and prosumers. For this, a case study from Delhi is considered and optimal investment options are assessed using an energy system optimization tool. Seven scenarios, including a business as usual (BAU) scenario, are evaluated.

If the DISCOM has access to sufficient rooftop area, it should aim at installing 3 MWp solar capacity under currently fixed electricity tariffs, or 2 MW if participating in the power market. Both would increase the DISCOM's profits. Battery storage does not pose an economically viable option considering the avoidance of expensive national grid imports. The installation of 500 kW PV on the DISCOM owned buildings is recommended which can increase the profit minorly and avoid penalties for not meeting RPO. The avoided penalty costs due to the RPO scheme are as high as the annuity of this investment.

Under current incentives, prosumerism is beneficial and would result in multiple rooftop solar systems of 13 MW aggregated capacity. The feasibility of such systems is questionable, both financially and due to the practical availability of rooftop areas. If prosumerism was limited to the targeted solar capacity of the Delhi government, 1.2 MW would be installed which would lower annual electricity bills. Considering self-consumption, investments in the battery is not an economic option for prosumers as it is more beneficial to feed-in into the distribution grid.

Prosumerism will decrease the DISCOM's revenues, but such an effect could be limited if the DISCOM takes initiative and installs 1.8 MW PV. In general, the DISCOM can benefit from rooftop solar installation and selling RECs. However, they also need to consider available rooftop area and might need to develop incentives for rooftop owners to be able to access their rooftops. Thus, it is recommended that they look for new business models (e.g., strategic partnership with building owners) to stay profitable and provide feedback to regulators to design appropriate incentives for prosumerism in their service area. Results also suggest that policymakers should re-design policies as prosumerism increases so that it doesn't put stress on government funds. Likewise, the policymakers should consider this development closely and consider new regulations and/or structures in the energy market, e.g., by providing a feed-in tariff for DISCOMs or by segregating grid and electricity retail business. Results from the study are relevant for designing future policy instruments.

Future research should evaluate the effect of considering no or limited feed-in tariffs for prosumers and no or limited REC selling options for DISCOMs, as these incentives are temporary policy measures. More work is needed to perform sensitivity analysis on key assumed inputs. The additional values offered by battery storage that are not considered in this study need to be evaluated to assess its economic value. Furthermore, new business models need to be investigated for DISCOMs so that they remain profitable under a new paradigm of prosumerism.

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